

SYNTHESIS OF CYANINE DYES BY THE CONDENSATION OF
p-DIALKYLAMINO BENZALDEHYDE WITH APPROPRIATE
HETEROCYCLIC COMPOUNDS. PART VI

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p-Dimethylamino- and *p*-diethylamino-benzaldehydes have been condensed with 6-chloro-, 6-bromo-, 6-iodo-quinaldine ethiodide and 6-formamido- and 6-acetamido-quinaldine ethiodide respectively. The effect on sensitisation of substitution in the quinaldine nuclei of *p*-diethylamino- and *p*-dimethylamino-cyanines has been studied. The optical, chemical, dyeing and photographic properties of these compounds have been examined and a few intermediates have been described.

Earlier workers have prepared cyanines from a variety of heterocyclic compounds containing reactive methyl groups. The fact that the styryl dyes are powerful photographic sensitisers was pointed out by Mills and Pope (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 946), who showed that the reaction, which proceeded smoothly in absolute alcohol with piperidine as a catalyst, was a general one. It is of interest therefore to investigate the nature of new cyanines produced in this manner by suitable substitutions, which latter are known to affect the sensitising power of the dyes. The present investigation was undertaken with this object.

Three new dyes have been prepared by introducing the chloro, bromo and iodo group respectively in the 6-position of 2-*p*-dimethylaminostyrylquinoline ethiodide and two more by introducing the formamido and acetamido group in the same position in 2-*p*-diethylaminostyrylquinoline ethiodide.

The dyes have all been recrystallised from methyl alcohol and obtained as well-formed pleochroic crystals, possessing various degrees of reflex. They are slightly soluble in cold water excepting the formamido and acetamido dyes, which dissolve only on prolonged heating. The rectified spirit solutions of the dyes are violet-red. The chief characteristics of the dyes are recorded in Table I. The relative resistances to decolorisation by *N*/100-HCl to 2 c.c. of 1/100,000 solutions of the different dyes in rectified spirit have been determined by titration and the comparative intensities of these solutions computed colorimetrically. Dimethylamino dyes have been found more resistant to decolorisation than the corresponding diethylamino compounds.

The dyes produced shades of varying colour on cotton, silk and wool, when dyed from alcoholic baths, as shown in Table II; but the shades were fugitive to sunlight and not fast to washing.

The yields of chloro, bromo and iodo dyes in the respective cases are 53.7%, 49.1% and 28.2%. This is difficult to explain, but the observations of Bennet *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1827; 1937, 1112) that among the halogens, iodine, the largest atom, controls its valence electrons less powerfully and the magnitude of the effect on neutralisation by electron relay is of the order $I > Br > Cl$, may have

something to do with it. It is noteworthy that the m.p.'s of the dimethylamino dyes are greater than those of the their diethyl analogues (cf. Doja and Banerjee, this *Journal*, 1946, 23, 222).

An interesting observation is that the acetic acid solutions of these dyes (with the exception of the chloro and the bromo derivatives) deepen in colour on warming. When the solutions are cooled, the intensity diminishes and the original colour is slowly regained. The formamido dye produces brownish yellow coloration on cooling and brownish red on warming. The effect is more pronounced in aqueous-acetic acid solution. This phenomenon has been previously reported in the case of cyanines derived from thiazoles (Doja and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*, p. 217).

The fluorescence of weak alcoholic solutions (1:100,000) of these dyes is shown in Table III (cf. Doja, *ibid.*, 1940, 17, 348).

The sensitisation and absorption spectra of these dyes are shown in Fig. 1. None of the halogen derivatives of these dyes are good sensitisers. The introduction of the chloro, bromo and iodo group in the 6-position of 2-*p*-dimethylaminostyryl-quinoline ethiodide depresses the sensitization as compared to 2-*p*-diethyl analogues. The formamido (E) and acetamido (F) dyes are remarkably good sensitisers, sensitizing up to 6900Å and 6800Å.

These somewhat unusual sensitising effects may be attributable to the association of the dye (Sheppard, *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, 1942, 14, 303; Scheibe, *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1936, 49, 563; 1937, 53, 51; Jelly, *Nature*, 1936, 138, 1009; 1937, 139, 631; Leermaker, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1937, 5, 878; Dickinson, *Phot. J.*, 1948, 88B, 97; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1947, 43, 486), its compactness (Brooker *et al.*, *J. Phot. Sci.*, 1953, 1, 173) and its planar configuration (West and Carrol, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1951, 19, 417), which individually or collectively are known to be important factors affecting the absorption and sensitisation of the dye.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-p-Dimethylaminostyryl-6-chloroquinoline Ethiodide.—6-Chloroquinaldine ethiodide (0.33 g.), *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.15 g.), absolute alcohol (15 c.c.) and piperidine (3 drops) were refluxed for 30 minutes on a small flame. The dye began to separate during the later period of heating and a further amount separated on cooling, yield 0.25 g. (53.7%). It was recrystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 266-67°. (Found: N, 6.13; Cl+I, 35.1. $C_{21}H_{22}N_2$ Cl I requires N, 6.0; Cl+I, 34.94 per cent).

2-p-Dimethylaminostyryl-6-bromoquinoline Ethiodide.—On boiling under reflux and a moisture-absorbing $CaCl_2$ tube, an absolute alcoholic solution (20.0 c.c.) of 6-bromoquinaldine ethiodide (0.76 g.), *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.30 g.) and two drops of piperidine, an intense magenta colour developed. The refluxing was continued for 45 minutes. The dye was obtained from the cold solution, yield 0.5 g. (49.1%); it was then recrystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 264°. (Found: N, 5.5; Br+I, 40.9. $C_{21}H_{22}N_2$ Br I requires N, 5.5; Br+I, 40.66 per cent).

FIG. I

TABLE I

Compound	Colour and shape of crystals.	Reflex.	Pleochroism. Colour of light in one position of polariser.	Colour after rotation through 90°.	Relative N/100 intensity of colour required.	Relative resistance to decolorisation.	Extra sensitisation. Total range of sensitization in Å.	Frequency of maximum absorption $\times 10^4 \text{Å}.$
B ₁	Dark grey felted clusters	Weak greenish white.	Weak green.	Glass like	3.49	45.10 c.c. 21.5	5200-6250 Uniform sensitization. No maximum.	55555
C ₁	Dirty mauve powder.	Pinkish white.	Colorless.	Pink.	4.04	44.35 21.1	Nil	55555
D ₁	Magenta-grey crystals.	White.	Dirty yellow.	Weak rose.	1.00	44.00 21.0	5100-6100 Faint maximum at 6000	55046
E	Green stunted needles	Scintillating green.	Bottle green.	Greenish yellow.	2.92	24.00 11.4	5200-6900 Uniform, no maximum.	57143
F	Sage-green shining platelets.	Strong yellowish green.	Light yellow	Dirty white.	4.42	2.10 1.0	5100-6800 Faint maximum at 5600	56075
	B ₁ -2- <i>p</i> -Dimethylaminostryl-6-chloroquinoline ethiodide.						C ₁ -2- <i>p</i> -Dimethylaminostryl-6-bromoquinoline ethiodide.	
	D ₁ -2- <i>p</i> -	"	"	"			K-2- <i>p</i> -Diethyl	"
	E-2- <i>p</i> -Diethyl	"	"	"			-6-formamido "	"
		"	"	"			-6-acetamido "	"

TABLE II

* Compound	B ₁	C ₁	D ₁	E	F
Silk	Weak reddish violet	Reddish violet	Pink	Pink	Indigo blue
Wool	Reddish violet	Deep reddish violet	Pink	Weak rose red	Reddish violet
Cotton	Reddish violet	Reddish violet	Light reddish violet	Violet-red	Indigo blue

* Refers to same numbering and nomenclature as in Table I.

TABLE III

Wallace colour filter number.	Colour of the fluorescent beam seen at right angles to the incident beam,					
	H ₁	C ₁	H ₂	H ₃	H ₄	F
1	Deep red.	Light absorbed.	Intense red.	Light absorbed.	Light absorbed.	Deep red.
2	Yellowish red.	Brilliant red.	Red.	Flaming red.	Flaming red.	Crimson.
3	Reddish violet.	Violet (with reddish tinge)	Reddish violet	Rose-red.	Rose-red.	Deep pink.
4	Yellowish red.	Bright orange-red.	Flaming red.	Orange-red.	Orange-red.	Yellowish red.
5	Greenish yellow.	Orange-yellow.	Yellow	Yellow with greenish tinge.	Yellow with greenish tinge.	Leucou-yellow
6	Yellow.	Light yellow.	Light absorbed.	Leucou yellow.	Leucou yellow.	Greenish yellow
7	Light green.	Blue-green.	Blue-green.	Yellowish green.	Yellowish green.	Green
8	Bluish green.	Bluish green.	Bluish green.	Bluish green	Bluish green	Bluish green
9	Blue-violet.	Blue.	Sapphire-blue.	Blue.	Blue.	Violet-blue
10	Light absorbed.	Weak yellow.	Light yellow.	Leucou-yellow.	Leucou-yellow.	Light absorbed.

2-p-Dimethylaminostyryl-6-iodoquinoline Ethiodide.—6-Iodoquinaldine ethiodide (0.4 g.), *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.15 g.); absolute alcohol (20 c.c.) and piperidine (4 drops) were boiled under reflux for 45 minutes. The dye began to separate even while the solution was boiling. On cooling, the dye separated as woolly clusters, yield 0.15 g. (28.2%). When purified with methyl alcohol, the dye had m.p. 271-72°. (Found: N, 4.9; I, 45.8. $C_{21}H_{22}N_2I_2$ requires N, 5.03; I, 45.6 per cent).

6-Formamidoquinaldine has been described by Browning, Cohen, Ellingworth, and Gulbransen, *Proc. Roy. Soc., London*, 1924, 96B, 317) and m.p. recorded, 131-32°. This compound has now been prepared by the method similar to Barger and Robinson for the preparation of 3-formamidoquinaldine (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2947). 6-Aminoquinaldine (2.1 g.) and formic acid (12.0 g.) were refluxed together for 3 hours. The liquid was then poured into water, sodium carbonate was added till alkaline, when an oily product floated on the surface and solidified after 24 to 48 hours. It was recrystallised from xylene, m.p. 133-34°, yield 1.0 g. (Found: N, 14.9. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{10}ON_2$: N, 15.0 per cent).

6-Formamidoquinaldine ethiodide was prepared by refluxing 6-formamidoquinaldine (1.0 g.) and ethyl iodide (0.5 c.c.) in nitrobenzene (5.0 c.c.) for 4 hours on the water-bath and then cooling. It was recrystallised from aqueous alcohol, yield 0.3 g., m.p. 240-43° (blackening from 237°). (Found: I, 36.6. $C_{13}H_{14}ON_2I$ requires I, 37.1 per cent).

2-p-Diethylaminostyryl-6-formamidoquinoline ethiodide was obtained by refluxing 6-formamidoquinaldine ethiodide (0.34 g.), *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.18 g.), absolute alcohol (15 c.c.) and piperidine (3 drops) for 6 hours. The solution was then concentrated to 6 c.c. and on cooling, crystals deposited, yield 0.12 g. (23.7%). The dye was recrystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 225-26°. (Found: N, 8.5; I, 25.4. $C_{24}H_{28}ON_3I$ requires N, 8.38; I, 25.3 per cent).

6-Acetamidoquinaldine ethiodide was prepared according to the method of Wilson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 556).

2-p-Diethylaminostyryl-6-acetamidoquinoline ethiodide was obtained by refluxing, under a moisture trap, a mixture of 6-acetamidoquinaldine ethiodide (0.45 g.) and *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.22 g.) in absolute alcohol (15 c.c.) with piperidine (2 drops) for 1½ hours, when the dye separated, yield 0.3 g. When recrystallised from methyl alcohol, the dye came down in rectangular plates, m.p. 251-52°. (Found: N, 7.95; I, 24.4. $C_{25}H_{30}ON_3I$ requires N, 8.1; I, 24.66 per cent).

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